

IMPORTANT SKILLS NECESSARY FOR A MANAGER IN THE FIELD OF PHYSICAL CULTURE AND SPORTS

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Annotation: This paper presents the knowledge, skills and abilities necessary to perform managerial functions in the field of physical culture and sports.

Key words: managerial activity, manager, sphere of physical culture and sports.

Management in the field of physical culture and sports develops and functions according to general laws and principles, rules and methods inherent in science, technology and management practice. Here are the main principles of sports management:

1. Emphasis on the prospect of growth and further development of a sports company (organization, enterprise).
2. Constant analysis of the economic and social situation, identification of problems and possible ways and means of solving them.
3. The choice of personnel policy (selection, placement of personnel in the workplace).
4. Choice of financial policy (determination of the expected level of profit).

The general concept of management in the field of physical culture and sports helps to understand the knowledge of what a leader in the field of sports should be able to do. According to foreign experts, a professionally working sports manager should have the following skills:

- technical;
- work with people;

- understanding the situation.

Technical skills characterize the leader from the standpoint of using a variety of methods, procedures and techniques in activities. Technical skills can be general and specific. General technical skills include the so-called "financial skills of the manager" (development of the budget, estimates, preparation of financial reports). These skills do not depend on the type of activity of the organization in which the manager works.

Managers working in the field of production of sports goods and the provision of physical culture and sports services must have specific, technical skills:

- 1) purely production skills;
- 2) the ability to use sports equipment, to establish the relationship between physical activity, diet.

The ability of a leader to work with people is characterized in terms of relationships with employees of the organization in which he works, or with employees of other organizations. If technical skills relate to working with things, then the ability to work with people is determined by its relationship with employees. A leader with this skill demonstrates the ability to individually understand the strengths and weaknesses, similarities and differences of employees.

Understanding the situation is the most difficult skill, it is associated with the ability of the leader to see the process of activity as a whole and determine the relationship of phenomena. Thanks to this quality, a manager in the field of physical culture and sports foresees how relationships can change in general or in separate components, depending on changes in a specific situation - production, political, economic and social.

A leader who has mastered the three skills has the skill of "connection" and can successfully implement the goals and objectives of management in the field of physical culture and sports.

To characterize the quality of management in the field of physical culture and sports, the concept of individual mastery is also used, which reflects the effective

use of personal time, the organization of thinking, the clear expression of thoughts, the introduction of innovations (innovations) in practical work.

There is a concept that a sports manager is a person who devotes a lot of time to perform his functions, and that it is not typical for him to perform routine work. However, the results of foreign studies show the fallacy of this opinion. A manager in the field of physical culture and sports is a person who is not only thinking and planning, but a person whose activity is characterized by a hard pace, the speed of performing a large number of permanent duties, including rituals, ceremonies, negotiations, meetings.

In modern market conditions, there are ten managerial roles, combined into three large groups:

1. Representation
2. Information role.
3. Regulatory role.

Representation is reflected in three specific roles:

- a) nominee boss,
- b) leader;
- c) a person making connections.

The role of a nominal boss is especially typical for managers of large organizations, and consists in representing the organization at a reception. The liaison's role is to establish and maintain external working contacts.

The informational role is also triune and includes the following functions:

- a) analytics;
- b) an informer;
- c) speaker.

In the role of an analyst, the manager collects information of interest, obtained both from all available external sources and from employees of his organization. Acting as an informant, the manager transmits the necessary information to his

subordinates. As a speaker, the manager can act both in his own organization and in other organizations, both in private and in public form.

The regulatory role is divided into four responsibilities:

- a) an entrepreneur;
- b) maintaining a normal working atmosphere;
- c) resource distributor;
- d) an intermediary.

As an entrepreneur, the manager introduces the achievements of science and technology into the production process to improve the efficiency of the organization. To maintain the efficiency of the team, the manager eliminates conflict situations that lead to disruption of the working atmosphere in the organization.

The role of the resource allocator is associated with the responsibility for the timely, equal and fair distribution of financial resources.

The role of an intermediary is performed in resolving various disputes, both between employees of the organization and between departments of the organization.

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